

Both direct and inverse conductometric titrations (Fig. 2, curves 3,4) showed the formation of the compound $2\text{UO}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{As}_2\text{S}_3$.

Fig. 2. Pyrothioarsenite titrations: (1) and (3) 0.1 M $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\text{UO}_2$, added to 25 ml of 0.004 M $\text{Na}_4\text{As}_2\text{S}_5$, (2) and (4) 0.2 M $\text{Na}_4\text{As}_2\text{S}_5$, added to 25 ml of 0.003 M $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\text{UO}_2$.

Investigations on the formation of metal-thioarsenite were not successful because the compound formed was not stable and decomposed to a yellow precipitate of As_2S_3 .

Analytical study: The different uranyl arsenites were prepared by mixing stoichiometric amounts of uranyl acetate and the respective sodium thioarsenites. The precipitates obtained were washed several times with aqueous 10% (v/v) ethanolic solution and dried in a vacuum desiccator for 40 h. A known amount (2 g) of each of the above was digested with concentrated HNO_3 (15 ml) to dryness on a steam-bath. The treatment was repeated several times. The residue was dissolved in minimum quantity of HCl and then analysed⁷ for U and As. Sulphur in the uranyl thioarsenites was determined gravimetrically⁷. The compositions of the compounds established through the above analysis were found to be the same as that obtained by the electrometric methods.

The present electrometric and analytical investigations confirm the formation and precipitation of $3\text{UO}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{As}_2\text{S}_3$ and $2\text{UO}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{As}_2\text{S}_3$ around pH 7.0 and 5.5, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The author expresses his sincere thanks to the CNPq, Brasilia, for the financial aid.

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Kinetics of Oxidation of Aliphatic Secondary Alcohols by *N*-Bromosaccharin

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Manuscript received 2 September 1982, revised 8 August 1983, accepted 8 May 1986

N-BROMOSACCHARIN (NBSA) has been used sporadically as an oxidising agent in organic chemistry¹. While the mechanism of oxidation of organic compounds by *N*-bromosaccharin (NBS) has been fairly well established²⁻⁴, the reactions of NBSA have not been elucidated from the mechanistic point of view. We have therefore attempted to study the reactions of a variety of organic substrates with NBSA with a view to arrive at the mechanisms of the reactions and also to compare the reactivities of the two reagents NBS and NBSA. We report in this note the results on the kinetics of the oxidation of aliphatic secondary alcohols by NBSA.

Experimental

N-Bromosaccharin was prepared by the addition of bromine to the sodium salt of saccharin at 0°. All other reactants were commercial samples, purified by either distillation or crystallisation. Acetic acid (A.R.) was further purified⁵. The kinetics were followed under pseudo-unimolecular conditions (alcohol \gg NBSA) by estimating the unreacted NBSA at various intervals of time by an iodometric procedure. The rate constants reported are the average of at least three kinetic runs and are reproducible within $\pm 5\%$.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of propan-2-ol, taken as a typical substrate, follows the rate law

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$-d[\text{NBSA}]/dt = k_2[\text{NBSA}][\text{Propan-2-ol}]$ in binary solvent mixtures of acetic acid and water in presence of 0.02 M mercury(II) acetate, added to prevent the interaction of the product Br^- ions with the oxidant⁸. The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.25 M with HClO_4 . The data in Table 1 reveal the individual rate dependence on the reactants. Although being acid-catalysed, no specific dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$ could be seen for the reaction. ($10^4 k_1$ in presence of 0.05 M and 0.2 M HClO_4 are 3.24 and 3.46 s^{-1} , respectively, in 50% aqueous acetic acid in presence of 0.02 M mercury(II)

TABLE 1—ORDER DEPENDANCE FOR OXIDATION OF PROPAN-2-OL BY N-BROMOSACCHARIN AT 30°

Solvent: 50% HOAc-50% H₂O, [Hg(OAc)₂]=0.02 M, $\mu=0.25$

[NBSA] M	[Propan-2-ol] M	$10^4 k_1$ s^{-1}	$10^3 k_2$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
0.001	0.020	2.62	1.31
0.002	0.020	2.63	1.31
0.003	0.020	2.63	1.31
0.004	0.020	2.62	1.31
0.002	0.040	5.02	1.26
0.002	0.050	6.15	1.23
0.002	0.100	12.9	1.29

acetate at 30°). Hg^{II} is also involved only as a complexing agent for the Br^- and does not oxidise the alcohol under the experimental conditions. The reaction rate also does not vary significantly with the increasing ionic strength of the medium. The reaction is indeed susceptible to variations in the polarity of the medium obtained by varying the acetic acid concentration in the solvent mixture. ($10^4 k$ values in 30 and 70% acetic acid are 1.69 and 3.70 s^{-1} , respectively. The concentrations of alcohol, NBSA, $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ are 0.02, 0.002 and 0.02 M, respectively, the ionic strength being 0.25). The rate of oxidation increases with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. Added saccharin decreases the rate of oxidation perceptibly (Table 2) indicating a prior equilibrium step involving the oxidant.

The effect of structural variations in the alcohol $\text{R}-\text{CH}_2\text{CHOH}-\text{CH}_3$ on the rate of oxidation, has been studied with a number of alcohols where R is an electron-withdrawing or an electron-releasing substituent. As in other oxidations with N-halogen compounds, these reaction rates are also considerably affected by the nature of the substituent

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ADDED SACCHARIN ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF PROPAN-2-OL BY NBSA IN 50% HOAc-50% H₂O AT 30°

[Propan-2-ol]=0.02 M, [Hg(OAc)₂]=0.02 M, [NBSA]=0.002 M, $\mu=0.25$

[Saccharin] M	$10^4 k_1$ s^{-1}
—	2.71
0.002	2.10
0.003	0.98
0.050	0.25

introduced (Table 3). A linear free energy correlation of the reaction rate with σ^* (Taft substituent constant) yields a reaction constant ρ^* equal to -2.3, a value similar to other alcohol oxidations by Br_2 or $\text{NBS}^{6,7}$. The thermodynamic parameters for the reaction are also included in the Table 3.

On the basis of the rate law and other observations mentioned above, the following mechanism is proposed for the oxidation.

The finer details of the slow step are more likely to be

rather than the one involving the formation of $\text{R}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CHOBr}-\text{CH}_3$ as an intermediate⁹; as in the latter case, one would expect a positive ρ^*

TABLE 3—SUBSTITUENT EFFECTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF ALCOHOLS BY NBSA

(R-CHOH-CH ₃) R	$10^3 k_2^*$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	E_a kcal mol^{-1}	ΔH^\ddagger kcal mol^{-1}	ΔS^\ddagger $\text{cal K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
CH_3	1.32	14.8	14.2	20
CH_3-CH_3	3.4	12.1	11.6	27
$n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$	3.8	10.7	10.1	32
$n\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{13}$	2.3	13.8	13.2	22
C_6H_5	0.211	—	—	—
CH_2Cl^a	0.187	—	—	—

* At 30°. * For $\text{ClOH}_2-\text{CHOH}-\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}$.

(consistent with an E_a type of elimination reaction) and base catalysis would also have been observed.

Further, a good linear correlation of the rates of oxidation of the aliphatic alcohols by NBSA with the rate constants for the oxidation of similar systems by NBS⁸ underscores a formal similarity of the two transition states.

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Equilibrium Studies of Interaction of Oxovanadium(II), Manganese(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) with *o*-Hydroxyacetophenone, 4-Methyl-5-hydroxy-6-acetylcoumarin and 1-(2'-Furyl)-3-(4'-methyl-5'-hydroxycoumarin-6'-yl)propane-1,3-dione

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Manuscript received 20 December 1980, revised 14 April 1986,
accepted 23 April 1986

UNSATURATED lactones are well known for their selective inhibition of growth of plant and animal tissues, for toxicity in fish, antibacterial and haemorrhagic activity and for their effect on central nervous system. Coumarins belong to this class of compounds¹. It was, therefore, decided to investigate the interactions of coumarins with metal ions commonly present in the living systems and to study the effect of substitution of various ring systems on coumarin moiety. The following ligands were selected for the present study.

Experimental

The ligands 1, 2 and 3 were prepared by following the procedures reported earlier²⁻⁴. The metal ions were used in the form of their perchlorates, except for vanadium, where vanadyl sulphate was used. The concentrations of the metal ions were determined complexometrically⁵ by EDTA titrations. Dioxane was purified⁶. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade. The titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere. The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titration of the solution of known amount of the ligands (1, 1.023×10^{-3} ; 2, 1.005×10^{-3} ; 3, 1.006×10^{-3} M), known amounts of free HClO_4 (5.234×10^{-3} M), in the absence and presence of known amounts of the metal ions (VO^{II} , 1.187×10^{-3} ; Mn^{II} , 1.327×10^{-3} ; Co^{II} , 1.167×10^{-3} ; Ni^{II} , 1.062×10^{-3} ; Cu^{II} , 9.704×10^{-3} M) with sodium hydroxide solution (2.469×10^{-1} M) at 0.1 M (NaClO_4) ionic strength.

Results and Discussion

The \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL values were calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti⁷. The results are stated in Table 1. The pK value of phenol in 50 : 50 (v/v) water-dioxane system was 12.0. In *o*-hydroxyacetophenone in spite of the electron withdrawing CH_3CO group, the value was found to be 12.06, probably due to the intra-molecular hydrogen bonding. The acidities of the coumarin and the diketone derivatives were comparatively higher than that of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone because of the electron withdrawing oxygen atoms attached to adjacent rings. Weak hydrogen bonding in the diketone derivative lowers its acidity to some extent.

With the exception of the VO^{II} complexes of acetophenone and diketone derivatives, the difference ($\log K_1 - \log K_2$) was less than 1.78, suggesting the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes by simultaneous equilibria⁸. In the VO^{II} complexes of the acetophenone and diketone derivatives, the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes were formed in stepwise manner. VO^{II} and Cu^{II} were found to form more stable complexes with all the three ligands (Table 1). Higher stability of these complexes could be attributed to the Jahn-Teller distortion⁹. The $\log K_A$ value of Cu^{II} complex of the